

Molecular Tailoring of Pyridine Core-Based Hole Selective Layer for Cs₂AgBiBr₆ Perovskite Solar Cells Fabrication

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Abstract

The lead-free double perovskite Cs₂AgBiBr₆ is vouched as an alternative solution to addressing the stability and toxicity issues associated with lead-based perovskite solar cells. However, in double perovskites, restricted charge transport impacts optoelectronic performance. By adopting interface engineering, we have designed a series of pyridine-based small molecules as hole selective materials, where four distinct arms are linked with the pyridine core. We decipher the structure–property–device performance relationship impacted by arm modulation. In the instance of **PyDAnCBZ** made of N³,N³,N⁶,N⁶-tetrakis(4-methoxyphenyl)-9H-carbazole-3,6-diamine arm linking with pyridine core, the arms robust interaction with the core leads to an effective hole extraction as evidenced by electrical, microstructure and spectroscopic experiments. The solar cells fabricated with **PyDAnCBZ** as hole selective layer measured an unparallel 2.90% power conversion efficiency, for Cs₂AgBiBr₆ solar cells. Our computed results suggest the road map to achieving ~5% efficiency with fine-tuning for Cs₂AgBiBr₆ solar cells. Our results offer a synergistic pathway to strengthen inorganic lead-free perovskite materials for photovoltaic applications and unravel the guidelines for building small molecules for electro-optical applications.

Keywords: Cs₂AgBiBr₆, small molecule, perovskite solar cells, electron paramagnetic resonance, photovoltaic simulation

1. Introduction

Organic-inorganic lead halide perovskite materials have shown remarkable optoelectrical and photovoltaics properties, and solution-processibility through cost-effective routes, this increases their acceptability as a potential candidate for next-generation photovoltaics (PV).^[1-4] However, their poor stability and the toxicity of lead restrict their scope for an immediate commercial endeavor.^[5-8] To close the gap, significant attempts are being made to exploit interface materials to improve stability^[9,10], and development of eco-friendly perovskite and its derivatives for PV ^[11,12].

Double metal perovskite $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ is a potentially attractive alternative for solar cells, attributed to its enhanced thermal stability, less toxicity, and favorable photoelectrical traits including long carrier lifespan and moderate charge carrier mobility.^[13-15] Attempts are being made to enhance the PV performance of $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ based devices. This includes innovative deposition processes^[14,16,17], dye sensitization,^[13,18,19] additive engineering,^[20-22] binary solvent,^[14,23] and interface engineering^[24-27] to assist high-quality film formation, which in turn facilitate carrier transport, and thus power conversion efficiency (PCE). Despite these advancements, the PCEs are far below compared to the 3D, Pb-based perovskites with comparable bandgaps. In this context, new attempts justify the investigation to boost PV performance.

Effective performance of $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ solar cells has been achieved by the typical device architect i.e. FTO/ESL/ $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ /HSL/Au (electron and hole selective layers are abbreviated as ESL and HSL). Among them, 2,2',7,7'-tetrakis-(*N,N*-di-*p*-methoxyphenyl-amine)-9,9'-spirobifluorene (Spiro-OMeTAD) provide facile implementation and is the widely investigated HSL.^[28] However, the mandatory hydrophilic doping of Spiro diminishes the stability merit of $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$. Additionally, the poor transport capacity of Spiro-OMeTAD will result in serve carrier recombination. Arguably, it is envisaged that the development of functionalized HSLs for $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ will allow performance and stability enhancement.

Small molecules with unique features offer prospective for application in lead-free $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$: low batch-to-batch variance, diversity via molecular design methodologies, and cost-effectiveness.^[29] The pyridine can be served as an electron-deficient and a passivation function unit to create new HSLs.^[30] Pyridine-based HSLs and associated synthesis methodologies have been reported.^[31,32] We have put forward, the linking topology of the pyridine core and common arms, as well as the *N*-position effects on pyridine-based HSLs.^[33,34]

The arm modulation based on pyridine-based HSLs, has not been probed yet. Notably, the incorporation of innovative small molecule HSLs in Cs₂AgBiBr₆ devices remains uninvestigated. In this study, we designed four pyridine-based HSLs using certain arms in the 2,6-position linking of pyridine: *N,N*-di-4-anisylamino (DAn), (*N,N*-bis(4-methoxyphenyl)aniline) (PDAn), (*N*³,*N*³,*N*⁶,*N*⁶-tetrakis(4-methoxyphenyl)-9H-carbazole-3,6-diamine) (DAnCBZ), and 4,4'-(10H-phenothiazine-3,7-diyl)bis(*N,N*-bis(4-methoxyphenyl)-aniline) (PTPDAn), named as **PyDAn**, **PyPDAn**, **PyDAnCBZ**, and **PyPTPDAn**, respectively. We employed an array of techniques to quantify the chemical and optoelectronic properties. Moreover, we fabricated Cs₂AgBiBr₆ based device employing pyridine-based HSLs, and the **PyDAnCBZ**-based devices showed superior performance than other HSLs. Furthermore, we computed the photovoltaic simulation to unravel the road map for the lead-free device performance enhancement method.

2. Results and discussion

2.1 Synthesis

Herein, we critically analyze arm modulation employing small molecules with a pyridine core and its 2,6-position linking topology. The DAn, PDAn, and DAnCBZ moieties have frequently been utilized as arms in the design of organic hole-selective materials.^[35] Moreover, PTPDAn, which consists of phenothiazine interacting with two PDAn arms, is the largest arm molecule. The synthetic routes of these materials are illustrated in Scheme 1. Four precursors were made using prior procedures that are detailed in the supporting information. The **PyDAn**, **PyDAnCBZ**, and **PyPTPDAn** were synthesized from the palladium acetate catalyzed Buchwald-Hartwig cross-coupling reaction with a yield of 70%, 46%, and 52%, respectively, while **PyPDAn** was synthesized by the Suzuki cross-coupling reaction using palladium-tetrakis(triphenylphosphine) as a catalyst and resulted in the final molecule with a yield of 60%. The molecular structures were established by ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR spectroscopy, and HRMS (Figure S1 in the supporting information). All the materials are soluble in common organic solvents.

Scheme 1. Synthetic route for **PyDAn**, **PyPDAn**, **PyDAnCBZ**, and **PyPTPDAn**.

2.2 Photophysical and electrochemical properties

The normalized optical absorption spectra of pyridine-based small molecules are presented (**Figure 1a**) and the data are compiled in **Table 1**. The spectra revealed two principal absorption bands: 250–310 nm and 340–420 nm, respectively. This is in line with previous results on other pyridine-based HSLs.^[33,36] The electronic transition causes an absorbed peak in the lower wavelength. The action of intramolecular charge transfer (ICT) between the armed group and the electron-deficient pyridine core produced a substantial peak in the 340–420 nm region. According to the formula $E_g^{\text{opt}} = 1240/\lambda_{\text{onset}}$, the optical bandgap (E_g^{opt}) values were calculated to be 3.04, 3.06, 2.85, and 3.11 eV, respectively,

Table 1. Photophysical and electrochemical data of the **PyDAn**, **PyPDAn**, **PyDAnCBZ**, and **PyPTPDAn**.

HSL	λ_{onset} (nm)	$\lambda_{\text{abs.max}}$ (nm)	$\lambda_{\text{PL max}}$ (nm)	$\Delta \lambda_{\text{Stokes}}$ (nm)	$E_g^{\text{opt}}/E_g^{\text{DFT}}$ (eV)	$E_{\text{onset}}^{\text{ox}}$ (eV)	E_{HOMO} (eV)	E_{LUMO} (eV)	T_d (°C)	T_g (°C)	Cond. ($\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$)	Mob. ($10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2 \text{V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$)
PyDAn	409	278	423	145	3.04/4.30	0.62	-5.02 ^a /-5.72 ^b	-2.60 ^a /-0.30 ^b	81.0	307.5	0.11	0.35
PyPDAn	405	363	506	143	3.06/4.19	0.54	-4.94 ^a /-5.64 ^b	-2.47 ^a /-0.98 ^b	82.0	372.5	1.23	1.85
PyDAnCBZ	436	308	480	172	2.85/3.30	0.36	-4.76 ^a /-5.45 ^b	-2.69 ^a /-0.85 ^b	—	242.0	2.11	3.50
PyPTPDAn	399	352	480	128	3.11/3.45	0.60	-5.00 ^a /-5.70 ^b	-2.35 ^a /-1.46 ^b	—	196.6	0.06	1.14

^a E_{HOMO} was estimated from the redox potential in the CV curves, and $E_{\text{LUMO}} = E_{\text{HOMO}} + E_g^{\text{opt}}$. ^b E_{HOMO} and E_{LUMO} were calculated by DFT results.

It can be deduced from Figure 1b, the highest peak was detected in the photoluminescent spectra of **PyDAn**, **PyPDAn**, **PyDAnCBZ**, and **PyPTPDAn** at 423, 506, 480, and 480 nm, with Stokes shifts of 145, 143, 172, and 128 nm, respectively. For organic materials, larger Stokes shifts result from a shift in the material's structure between the ground and excited states. It was observed that **PyDAnCBZ** has a larger Stokes shift than the others, which occurs from the modification of the geometrical configuration generated by fluorescence illumination and can enhance the capacity to fill pores, leading to higher charge transporting ability.^[37,38]

The energy levels of HSLs were measured using cyclic voltammetry (Figure 1c & Figure S2). The **PyDAn** and **PyPDAn** showed only one reversible event, while the **PyDAnCBZ** and **PyPTPDAn** showed two reversible anodic events. Two DAn units connect to a carbazole in the **PyDAnCBZ**'s molecular configuration, and two PDAn units connect to a phenothiazine in **PyPTPDAn**'s, which may form stable dicationic species owing to charge delocalization throughout the conjugation chain, whereas **PyDAn** and **PyPDAn** can only undergo single cation transformation. The **PyDAn**, **PyPDAn**, **PyDAnCBZ**, and **PyPTPDAn** have starting oxidation potentials of 0.62, 0.54, 0.36, and 0.60 eV, respectively. The **DAnCBZ** arm's greater electron donation than other arms contributed to **PyDAnCBZ**'s lower oxidation potential. E_{HOMO} of these compounds was -5.02, -4.94, -4.76, and -5.00 eV, respectively, calculated from $E_{\text{HOMO}} = -4.4 + E_{\text{onset}}^{\text{ox}}$. The corresponding E_{LUOMO} was calculated by adding $E_{\text{g}}^{\text{opt}}$ to the E_{HOMO} and summarized in Table 1.

Figure 1. (a) Normalized UV-vis absorption spectra, (b) photoluminescent spectra, (c) cyclic voltammograms, and (d) differential scanning calorimetry curves of **PyDAn**, **PyPDAn**, **PyDAnCBZ**, and **PyPTPDAn**. (e) I - V curves for conductivity measurement, and (f) J - V curves of mobility measurement for the hole-only device with these HSLs.

To unravel the energy level and the geometrical structure of pyridine-based HSLs, we performed density functional theory (DFT) studies at the B3LYP/6-31G(d,p) (Figure S3). The E_{LUMO} and E_{HOMO} of **PyDAn** spread over the pyridine core and diphenylamine arms, and the E_{HOMO} of **PyPDAn** exhibits similarities in the electron densities with **PyDAn**, while the E_{LUMO} of **PyPDAn** is distributed on the central pyridine and benzene bridge. The E_{HOMO} of **PyDAnCBZ** was mainly distributed on DAnCBZ arms, and E_{LUMO} was mainly distributed on the pyridine core. The E_{LUMO} and E_{HOMO} were distributed on the pyridine core and PTPDAn arms in the **PyPTPDAn**. The trend of E_{LUMO} and E_{HOMO} values are paired with the cyclic voltammetry results.

To study the thermal properties of pyridine-based materials, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) were utilized. TGA curves (Figure S4), the decomposition temperatures (T_d) corresponding to 5% with loss temperature were 307.5, 372.5, 242, and 196.6 °C for **PyDAn**, **PyPDAn**, **PyDAnCBZ**, and **PyPTPDAn**, respectively. It can be deduced that the T_d of pyridine-core based materials decreases as the arm size increases. The full and the second heating run of DSC are presented (Figure S5 and Figure 1d). The **PyDAn** display

an evident glass-transition temperature (T_g) at 81.0 °C and melting of the crystals (T_m) at 165.4 °C, whereas **PyPDAn** displayed an apparent T_g at 82.0 °C. The **PyDAnCBZ** and **PyPTPDAn** did not have an obvious T_g , showing their amorphous nature. The larger arms can enhance T_g , and **PyDAnCBZ** (**PyPTPDAn**) has improved its thermal stability and is beneficial for success in the real operating conditions of solar cells.

The electrical experiments were carried out to clarify the impacts of the arm on the HSLs ability for transport. The **PyDAn**, **PyPDAn**, **PyDAnCBZ**, and **PyPTPDAn** have conductivities values of 0.11, 1.23, 2.11, and 0.06 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$, respectively, estimated from Figure 1e. The hole mobilities of the pristine HSLs were 0.35, 1.85, 3.50, and 1.14 ($\times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$), respectively, according to the space charge limited currents (SCLC) technique (Figure 1f). The highest transporting value of **PyDAnCBZ**, as compared to others derives from the improved intramolecular charge transfer and uniform morphology subsequently discussed.

Electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) spectroscopy is an advantageous technique to identify molecules with unpaired electrons and to evaluate the relative number of spins and their mobility. For this purpose, X-band EPR experiments on pristine and doped 25 mM toluene solutions of the four pyridine-based HSLs were performed at room temperature (**Figure 2**). The EPR signal of the undoped samples was difficult to detect due to the number of spins inside the resonant cavity being practically below the detection limit of the spectrometer (about 10^9). In contrast, a dramatic enhancement of the signal was observed after the addition of lithium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide (LiTFSI) and 4-tert butylpyridine (*t*-BP), confirming a remarkable number of holes in these materials after LiTFSI-doping ($\approx 10^{17}$ spin/mol). The structure of the spectra, three equally spaced lines with intensity ratios close to 1:1:1, indicates that the unpaired electrons are preferentially located on ^{14}N nuclei ($I=1$), but the generation of other radicals with very short lifetime ($<10^{-6}$ s) cannot be disregarded. The absence of proton hyperfine structure is attributed to the presence of many protons with small hyperfine couplings. The spectra could be fitted to obtain the g value, the coupling parameter a^{N} , and the peak-to-peak linewidth (Table S1). The calculated g values (2.0044, 2.0040, 2.0037, and 2.0043 for **PyDAn**, **PyPDAn**, **PyDAnCBZ**, and **PyPTPDAn**, respectively) are in good agreement with those expected for N-centered cation radicals with the low orbital contribution to the ground state. The hyperfine coupling constant (a^{N}) and the peak-to-peak linewidth are relatively larger for **PyDAnCBZ** (6.8

and 4.8 Gauss, respectively) than for the other compounds, suggesting a higher spin density near the pyridine core.

Figure 2. Room temperature EPR spectra registered on 25 mM toluene solutions at X-band. The dotted lines represent the best fits obtained using the spectral parameters listed in Table S1.

Before the fabrication of the device, the surface properties and film-formation capabilities of HSLs were investigated. The $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ film was prepared using the hot-casting method, and as a result of the rapid crystallization, the as-prepared films (Figure S6) showed micrometer-sized agglomerates on the surface measured by scanning electron microscopy (SEM), which is equivalent with the results reported by Shao *et al* and Bein *et al*, respectively.^[14,39] The images of perovskite with HSLs atop the perovskite were presented (Figure S7). The perovskite/**PyDAn** exhibited subpar surface morphologies, whereas others show uniform coverage. To evaluate the morphology properties of HSLs, the HSLs were deposited on flat substrates. It showed that the **PyDAnCBZ** film had a remarkably uniform, smooth, and nanoparticle-free surface. In contrast, **PyDAn** and **PyPTPDAn** films display non-uniform coverage, whereas **PyPDAn** displayed aggregation and undissolved dopants.

2.3 Device performance

We fabricated PSCs with the *n-i-p* structure with FTO/*b&mp*- TiO_2 / $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ /HSL/Au to assess how the arm modulation of pyridine based-HSLs affected the PV performance. The cross-sectional SEM image of the PSC (Figure S8) reveals distinct layered topologies, with perovskite and **PyDAnCBZ** having thicknesses of 232 and 180 nm, respectively. The mesoporous TiO_2 ESL was chosen to improve the thickness of $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ for absorbing more light. The same precursor weight concentration was used to uniform the HSLs. The *J-V* curves of the optimized device

measured under standard AM 1.5G irradiation were presented in **Figure 3a** and summarized in Table 2.

Figure 3. (a) J - V curves and (b) EQE spectra, and (c) corresponding integrated current density of the Cs₂AgBiBr₆ solar cells with different HSLs. (d) the stabilized power output of the champion device with **PyDAnCBZ** HSL. (e) The PV performance of PSC with **PyDAnCBZ** aged under dry air and multi-stress (moisture and thermal) conditions.

The PSCs based on **PyDAnCBZ** attained a record PCE of 2.92% measured under reverse scan ($V_{oc} = 1059.0$ mV, $J_{sc} = 3.73$ mA cm⁻², and $FF = 74.0\%$), whereas lower PCEs were achieved by the devices with **PyPDAn** under similar conditions. The **PyPDAn**-based PSCs delivered a PCE of 1.90% ($V_{oc} = 1053.2$ mV, $J_{sc} = 2.76$ mA cm⁻², and $FF = 65.4\%$). The **PyDAn**- and **PyPTPDAn**-based PSCs yielded $\sim 1\%$ efficiency. The performance of the devices based on the new HSLs was in the following order: **PyDAnCBZ** > **PyPDAn** > **PyDAn** > **PyPTPDAn**. The reproducibility of the PSCs with the **PyDAnCBZ** was analyzed, and the PV performance is presented (Table S2) with an average PCE of $\sim 2.7\%$. Our findings demonstrate that **PyDAnCBZ** and **PyDAn** as HSL achieved a higher V_{oc} and FF than that of **PyDAn** and **PyPTPDAn**. The **PyDAnCBZ**-based device showed the highest performance owing to the higher FF and J_{sc} , which stems from the improved

electrical conductivity and hole mobility and inhibited surface charge carrier recombination. The J - V curves of PSCs measured under forward and reverse scans (Figure S9), and the calculated HI for PSCs with **PyDAn**, **PyPDAn**, **PyDAnCBZ**, and **PyPTPDAn** is 0.23, -0.07, 0.09, and -0.18, respectively. The **PyPDAn** and **PyDAnCBZ**-based PSCs showed a reduction in hysteresis in comparison with the others, which is consistent with the devices PV performance and we attribute to the improved charge-transporting abilities.

Table 2. The PV parameters of the PSCs with HSLs, and diode characteristics of the corresponding cells extracted from the J - V curves measured under dark conditions.

HSL	V_{oc} (mV)	J_{sc} (mA cm ⁻²)	FF (%)	PCE (%)	J (mA cm ⁻²)	R_s (Ω)	R_{sh} (k Ω cm ²)	n	J_0 (mA cm ⁻²)
PyDAn	1011.5	2.21	48.3	1.08	2.28	31	6.8	3.00	2.45×10^{-07}
PyPDAn	1053.2	2.76	65.4	1.90	2.55	23	7.3	2.96	2.78×10^{-07}
PyDAnCBZ	1059.0	3.73	74.0	2.92	3.48	30	11.4	2.31	9.18×10^{-09}
PyPTPDAn	852.1	2.36	45.2	0.91	2.33	46	7.0	4.30	1.27×10^{-04}

The external quantum efficiency (EQE) curves displayed that the PSCs with **PyDAnCBZ** have a higher EQE value at the whole wavelength than that of the others, with higher values of 69.8% and 72.4% at 365 and 440 nm, respectively. Additionally, the **PyDAnCBZ**-based device displayed higher EQE value across a wider wavelength range (700–1100 nm) as shown in Figure S10. It produced an enhanced integrated current density (J_{int}) of 3.48 mA cm⁻², which is higher than the majority of previously reported Cs₂AgBiBr₆-based devices.^[40,41] The outcomes are in line with those of the **PyDAnCBZ** with the highest J_{sc} (3.73 mA cm⁻²). The maximum power point tracking for champion **PyDAnCBZ** HSL under 1 Sun condition and electrical bias was conducted. The stabilized current density and PCE values (Figure 3d) of the device were 3.60 mA cm⁻² and 2.79%, respectively, which is in agreement with the PV performance.

We conducted the device stability to access the reliability of lead-free solar. The PCEs of **PyDAnCBZ**-based devices still had around 90% of their initial value after aging at the dry box with 10–30% relative humidity and room temperature for a thousand hours (Figure 3d). The V_{oc} and J_{sc} maintained the initial value, while the FF decreased to 90% of the initial value and was the cause of the slight deterioration of device performance.

The intrinsic ionic nature of double metal perovskite is prone to ion migration and impairs PV performance.^[42,43] Therefore, we assessed how the PV performed when subjected to multi-

stress with thermal (85 °C) and ambient moisture conditions. The PCE still had 92 percent of its original value after aging around 150 hours. We ascribed the excellent stabilities obtained to the additional bonds between the silver ions on the perovskite surface with HSLs, as well as the improvement of the diffusion barrier that prevents the Ag and Br ions from migrating. Importantly, the **PyDAnCBZ** possessed amorphous forms and could maintain its transporting properties under thermal aging. The phenomena constrained by **PyDAnCBZ** can be further quantified.

To elucidate the charge transport kinetics properties of the lead-free PSCs, complementary electrical characterizations were performed. Figure S11 represented the $J-V$ curve of the PSCs measured under dark conditions, and the diode parameters extracted are represented in Table 2. The series resistance (R_s) is high for all PSCs, since typical lead-based PSCs present values of R_s an order of magnitude of 1 Ω . Nevertheless, this value may be due to the resistive TiO_2 , having the HSL a low impact. The shunt resistance (R_{sh}) value is good in all the PSCs, indicating that there are no shunt sources between the electrodes, such as pinholes or conductive phases. The dark saturation current (J_0) can be associated with the carrier recombination in the cells, which correlates with the open circuit voltage.^[7] Compared to the other PSCs, the **PyDAnCBZ**-based cell shows a lower dark saturation current, correlating with the V_{oc} values measured in Figure 1a. Suggesting **PyDAnCBZ** employment largely mitigates the recombination, most likely in the back surface, while the other pyridine HSLs present larger surface recombination. The diode ideality factor close to 2 is a typical value for thin film PV, which indicates that the carrier recombination occurs in the depletion area. Larger values of the ideality factor may indicate that other sources of recombination can affect the PV parameters, degrading the FF . **PyDAnCBZ**-based devices show a lower ideality factor, indicating the HSL ability to control the recombination process.

Additionally, we performed capacitance-voltage measurements and derived Mott-Schottky plots (**Figure 4a–4d**). In a solar cell with a diode behavior, the region of the negative slope of a Mott-Schottky plot indicates the reduction of the depletion region with the increase of the voltage, from where the built-in potential can be calculated as in the case of the **PyDAnCBZ**. However, in the other solar cells studied, a positive slope is also found, which suggests a barrier for the charge carrier has emerged, due to their poor charge carrier ability. This barrier may explain the increase of recombination found in the dark $J-V$ curves for these cells. Since this barrier does not allow the extraction of more parameters in these cells with reliability, the rest of the measurements were made only in the **PyDAnCBZ** solar cell. From the capacitance-voltage measurements, the carrier

density and depletion width were calculated (Figure 4e), revealing the doping density of the $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ is $2.46 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, while the depletion at 0 V is 107 nm. This is found to be the first bottleneck for the performance of $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ as a light-absorbing layer, since the charge collection is limited, narrowing the photocurrent that can be extracted.

The measurement of the impedance in the vicinity of the turn-on voltage (Figure S12) and we calculated the transfer time from this (Figure 4f). This parameter represents the time for a charge to recombine once is in the depletion region. A value in the order of 1 μs in the region of the maximum power point voltage is high enough to consider that losses by recombination in the junction are negligible.

Figure 4. Capacitance-voltage spectra of PSCs using (a) **PyDAn**, (b) **PyPDAn**, (c) **PyDAnCBZ**, and (d) **PyPTPDAn** as HSL, with the estimation of the built-in potential when possible. (e) Carrier density is calculated from the capacitance-voltage. (e) Impedance spectra in the vicinity of the maximum power point voltage and (g) transfer time calculated for the **PyDAnCBZ**.

To determine the effects found bottleneck for lead-free $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ solar cells, the PV performance was simulated using PC1D software, combining the results obtained from the characterization with the properties of $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$.^[14,44] The energy levels of the solar cell, including the FTO, TiO_2 , $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$, and HSL, are shown in **Figure 5a**. It can be observed that

the depletion region of the solar cell simulated is in the order of 100 nm, in agreement with the value calculated by the capacitance-voltage, due to the high doping density of $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$. When simulating the device performance, it can be noted that the baseline simulation of the $J-V$ curve and EQE calculated is close to the spectra of the **PyDAnCBZ** solar cell, as well as the PV characteristics (**Table 3**). Tuning of some of the key properties identified as bottlenecks was performed. First, a reduction of the doping density to a value of 10^{16} cm^{-3} allows for a higher collection of charge, increasing the current from 3.55 to 4.92 mA cm^{-2} , and the PCE by 1 %. A decrease in the doping density could be possible by controlling the defects and crystallinity of the $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ films. Then, the effect of the excessive series resistance found was analyzed. A reduction of an order of magnitude has a large impact on the FF, increasing from 69% to 77%.

Another problem for $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ PSCs reported is very low electron mobility, which impacts the charge collection and avoids the possibility of increasing the thickness of the $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ layer.^[45] Improving the electron mobility by reducing the electron traps in the perovskite layer has a small impact in thin cells, but may allow for an increase in the light-absorbing layer thickness without affecting other parameters. The effect of increasing the electron mobility and thickness was simulated, founding a significant increase in the photocurrent, (Figure 5b and 5c). Including all the modifications mentioned, the device based on $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ with the configuration used in this work, has the potential of reaching a PCE of a 4.9 %.

Figure 5. (a) Energy levels of the simulated device, (b) $J-V$ curves of the simulated solar cell, (c) EQE of simulated devices.

Table 3. Photovoltaic properties of the simulated device with the modified properties.

	V_{oc} (V)	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	FF (%)	PCE (%)	Doping density ($\times 10^{16}$ cm ⁻³)	μ_e (cm ² /Vs)	R_s (Ω)	Thickness (μ m)
Baseline	1.07	3.55	71	2.7	24.6	0.08	30	0.7
N_D decrease	1.12	4.92	69	3.81	1.0	0.08	30	0.7
R_s decrease	1.12	4.96	77	4.28	1.0	0.08	3	0.7
μ_e increase	1.12	5.04	80	4.53	1.0	0.3	3	0.7
Double thickness	1.13	5.51	79	4.90	1.0	0.3	3	1.4

3. Experimental Section

3.1 Design and Synthetic of pyridine core-based HSLs

Synthesis of PyDAn. All the oxygen or moisture sensitive reactions were carried out under an argon atmosphere and the reflux reactions were performed in an oil bath. A mixture of 2,6-dibromopyridine (0.5g, 2.11 mmol), bis(4-methoxyphenyl)amine (0.965 g, 4.22 mmol), palladium acetate (0.019 g, 0.084 mmol), 1,1'-ferrocenediyl-bis(diphenylphosphine) (0.116 g, 0.211 mmol) and sodium tert-butoxide (0.6 g, 6.33 mmol) in toluene (20 mL) was stirred at 110 °C for 24 h. After cooling down the reaction to room temperature, the mixture was diluted with dichloromethane and washed with water. The organic layer was dried over Na₂SO₄ and evaporated. The crude product was purified by column chromatography (hexane/CH₂Cl₂ = 3/1 vol/vol) to obtain **PyDAn** (0.625 g, 70% yield) as an off-white solid.

Synthesis of PyPDAn. A mixture of 4-Methoxy-N-(4-methoxyphenyl)-N-(4-(4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)phenyl)aniline (0.722 g, 0.84 mmol), 2,6-dibromopyridine (0.200 g, 0.84 mmol) and Pd(PPh₃)₄ (0.048 g, 0.042 mmol) in toluene (24 mL), ethanol (12 mL) and 2M K₂CO₃ aqueous solution (3 mL) was stirred at 100 °C for 24 h under an argon atmosphere. After cooling down the reaction to room temperature, the mixture was diluted with dichloromethane and washed with water. The organic layer was dried over Na₂SO₄ and evaporated. The crude product was purified by column chromatography (SiO₂, Hexane/CH₂Cl₂ = 1/4 vol/vol) to obtain **PyPDAn** (0.350 g, 60% yield) as an off-white solid.

Synthesis of PyPTPDAn. 2,6-bromopyridine (100 mg, 0.42 mmol), PTPDAn (0.86 g, 1.05 mmol), sodium tert-butoxide (366.9 mg, 3.822 mmol), and dry toluene (40 mL) were mixed in a flask and purged with N₂ for 10 min and P(^tBu)₃HBF₄ (9.23 mg, 0.05 mmol) and Pd(OAc)₂ (5.72 mg, 0.04 mmol) were added. The reaction was refluxed under N₂ for 48 h. After completion of the

reaction, monitored with TLC, the reaction was allowed to cool to room temperature and the solution was filtered to remove insoluble solids. The filtrate was concentrated in vacuo and purified by column chromatography (silica gel, hexane: ethyl acetate 8:4 (v/v) as eluent) to give **PyPTPDAn** as a greenish-yellow solid with a yield of 52%. All of the characterization for the novel HSL including $^1\text{H}/^{13}\text{C}$ NMR spectroscopy and mass spectra are shown in Supporting Information. The synthesis route of **PyDAnCBZ** has been reported by the reported literature from our group.^[34]

3.2 Device fabrication

The configuration of the PSCs is FTO/*b&mp*-TiO₂/Cs₂AgBiBr₆/HSL/Au. The FTO glass substrates (NSG10) were first cleaned with 2% Hellmanex solution, acetone, and isopropanol, respectively. The pre-cleaned substrates treated with UV-ozone were heated to 500 °C for over 30 min. The blocking TiO₂ was sprayed with the solution [1 mL of titanium (IV) diisopropoxide bis(acetylacetonate) was dissolved in 19 mL of ethanol]. These substrates were kept heating for 30 min after spray deposition. The mesoporous TiO₂ film was spin-coated at 4000 rpm for 30 s using the 0.13 g/mL 30NRD ethanol solution. The as-prepared *mp*-TiO₂ was post-heated at 125 °C for 15 min and 500 °C for 30 min. Then, the *mp*-TiO₂ layer was impregnated in an aqueous TiCl₄ solution (67.5 μL TiCl₄ in 10 mL deionized water) at 70 °C for 1 h, followed by sintered at 500 °C for 30 min again.

The Cs₂AgBiBr₆ precursor solution was prepared by dissolving 2 mmol CsBr, 1 mmol AgBr, and 1 mmol BiBr₃ in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), which was stirred at 100 °C until these salts were fully dissolved in DMSO. Both the FTO/*b&mp*-TiO₂ substrate and the precursor solution were placed on the hot plate at 80 °C and the solution was then spin-coated on the aforementioned substrate at 3000 rpm for 30 s, which was subsequently annealed at 280 °C for 5 min in the glovebox with argon. The ~ 40 mg/mL **PyDAn**, **PyPDAn**, **PyDAnCBZ**, and **PyPTPDAn** with 75, 60, 30, and 25 mM were dissolved in chlorobenzene, respectively, and the dopants were then added and their molar ratio of LiTFSI and *t*-BP was fixed to 0.5 and 3.3 to the materials (Li salt solution is 520 mg mL⁻¹ in acetonitrile). The precursor HSL solutions were then spin-coated atop perovskite film at 3,000 rpm for 30 s. Finally, a 70 nm thick gold electrode was thermally deposited.

3.3 Characterization

^1H NMR spectra were recorded using a 400 MHz spectrometer. Chemical shifts are reported in delta expressed in parts per million (ppm) downfield from tetramethylsilane (TMS) using residual protonated solvent as an internal standard $\{\text{CDCl}_3, 7.26 \text{ ppm}\}$. ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded using a 100 MHz spectrometer. Chemical shifts are reported in delta (d) units, expressed in parts per million (ppm) downfield from tetramethylsilane (TMS) using the solvent as an internal standard $\{\text{CDCl}_3, 77.16 \text{ ppm}\}$. The ^1H NMR splitting patterns have been described as “s, singlet; d, doublet; t, triplet; and m, multiplet”. HRMS were recorded on a Bruker-Daltonics micrOTOF-Q II mass spectrometer. UV-visible absorption spectra of all compounds were recorded on a PerkinElmer Lambda 35 UV-visible spectrophotometer in dichloromethane solution. Cyclic voltammograms were recorded on a CHI620D electrochemical analyzer (potentiostat) in dichloromethane solvent using glassy carbon as the working electrode, Pt wire as the counter electrode, and saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as the reference electrode. The scan rate was 100 mV s^{-1} for cyclic voltammetry. A solution of tetrabutylammonium hexafluorophosphate (TBAPF_6) in dichloromethane (0.1 M) was used as the supporting electrolyte.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was carried out using Mettler Toledo TGA/DSC 1 at a heating rate of $5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ under a nitrogen atmosphere. The glass transition temperature for the pyridine-based HSLs was recorded by differential scanning calorimetry (Pekin Elmer Diamond DSC) with a scan rate of 10 min^{-1} under N_2 gas flow. The second curve was analyzed. The SEM images were recorded by Hitachi S- 4800.

EPR spectra were performed at room temperature using a Bruker ELEXSYS E500 spectrometer operating at the X-band. The spectrometer was equipped with a superhigh-Q resonator ER-4123-SHQ. Toluene solutions of undoped and doped samples were placed in quartz tubes and spectra were recorded using typical modulation amplitudes of 1.0 G at a frequency of 100 kHz. The magnetic field was calibrated by an NMR probe and the frequency inside the cavity ($\sim 9.4 \text{ GHz}$) was determined with an integrated MW-frequency counter. The radical concentration was evaluated by integrating the EPR spectrum twice and by comparing it with a standard $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ sample. Data were collected and processed using the Bruker Xepr suite.

The J - V curves of the solar cells with an active area of 0.09 cm^2 controlled by a metal mask were measured under AM 1.5G illumination that was provided by 3A grade solar simulator (Newport). The forward scan range is 0 V to 1.3 V, and the reverse scan range is from 1.3 V to 0

V (scan rate: 10 mV s⁻¹). The EQE was measured by a 150 W Xenon lamp (Newport) attached to IQE200B (Oriel) motorized 1/4m monochromator as the light source. The impedance of devices was tested by Bio-logic SP-300 under different voltages in different frequencies. The device with structure: FTO/HSL/Au, and FTO/PEDOT:PSS/HSL/Au were fabricated and measured under dark conditions for calculating conductivity and mobility.

Impedance and capacitance-voltage measurements were performed inside a faraday box with a Biologic impedance analyzer, following the reported literature,^[46,47] by applying a 20 mV perturbation in a frequency range from 1GHz to 100 Hz, and applied constant voltage from -0.5 V to 1.5 V. EC-lab software were used to fit the equivalent circuits.

4. Conclusion

We developed and evaluated four pyridine-based small molecules as a p-type selective material, investigated the effect of arm size on the electro-optical characteristics, and found that arm modulation affects the electro-optical qualities. The lead-free solar cells fabricated with **PyDAnCBZ** outperformed others. The solar cells with **PyDAnCBZ** HSL showed excellent stability under moisture and thermal conditions. Furthermore, electrical investigations demonstrated that **PyDAnCBZ** aids in charge carrier transport. The roadmap was suggested through the photovoltaic performance simulation findings that with fine-tuning, the Cs₂AgBiBr₆ solar cells can improve to 4.9% efficiency.

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Supporting Information: Materials synthesis its spectroscopic and structural characterization, and device electrical properties are presented.

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